

Utilizing Artificial Intelligence for Financial Risk Monitoring in Asset Management

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Abstract: This paper explores the application and advantages of artificial intelligence (AI) in financial risk monitoring in asset management. With the increasing dynamics and complexity of the financial market, traditional risk management methods are insufficient to cope with the changing market environment. To this end, this paper assesses how AI technologies, specifically machine learning and deep learning models, can provide new solutions for risk prediction, identification, and management. The paper first reviews the traditional methods of financial risk monitoring, and their limitations then introduces the core concepts and techniques of artificial intelligence technology, including supervised, unsupervised, deep, and others. Through a systematic analysis of existing AI application cases, this paper explores how these technologies can improve the accuracy of risk identification, optimize asset allocation, and enhance the effectiveness of investment decisions. In particular, deep learning models have demonstrated a strong ability to process complex data patterns and predict market trends, enabling asset management to respond more quickly and accurately to unexpected events. The paper also discusses the practical application challenges of AI in financial risk monitoring, including data quality issues, interpretability of models, and implementation costs of the technology. This paper summarizes the best practices of AI technology in asset management through a comprehensive case study and data analysis. It proposes future research directions and policy recommendations to promote further the technology development and application promotion in this field.

Keywords: Cloud Computing Pricing, Economic Efficiency, Resource Management, Cost Optimization.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The rapid acceleration of digitalization and intelligence, along with the emergence of new technologies and models, has transformed the business operations landscape. The evolving global economic environment has increased the risks companies face, making "comprehensive control and efficiency enhancement" a critical consideration for businesses. As technologies such as Big Data, Artificial Intelligence (AI) [1], Cloud Computing, and the Internet of Things (IoT) continue to advance at a breakneck pace, many organizations are leveraging modern technological innovations to drive the digital transformation of their budgeting processes. This shift is leading to the continuous optimization of budgeting methods and the creation of innovative budgeting models.

The rapid development of Big Data and machine learning technologies presents new opportunities and challenges for corporate budgeting. [2] Due to enterprises' growing scale and complexity, traditional manual budgeting

methods are increasingly inadequate for meeting the demands of precise and timely information. Big Data provides vast information resources that can uncover underlying patterns and trends when analyzed through machine learning. By delving into these data insights, companies can better understand their operational status and market environment, leading to improved budgeting management. [3] Thus, research into machine learning-based budgeting management has emerged as a crucial area. Employing Big Data and machine learning technologies can enhance budgeting practices, provide scientific evidence for decision-making and strategic planning, and ultimately help businesses achieve greater economic efficiency and competitive advantage.

This paper explores the application of Artificial Intelligence in financial risk monitoring within asset management. [4][5] By integrating advanced machine learning techniques, the study aims to demonstrate how AI can enhance the accuracy and effectiveness of financial risk assessments. The research will focus on implementing AI-driven models to monitor and manage financial risks, offering

insights into their practical applications and benefits for asset management professionals.

2 RELATED WORK

2.1 THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS AND

APPLICATIONS OF BIG DATA IN FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT

As a product of advanced information development, data is central to Big Data. The essence of Big Data lies in extracting valuable and actionable insights from vast datasets. Domestically and internationally, scholars have explored Big Data from various theoretical and practical perspectives. Barwick (2012) emphasized that value is a fundamental requirement for Big Data, asserting that its value dictates the necessity for research and useful application. Mayer-Schönberger and Cukier (2012) highlighted that Big Data shifts focus from precision to complexity, reflecting its impact on analytical approaches. Wei and Jiang (2014) noted that the evolution of data collection methods has significantly influenced statistical analysis, expanding the scope from traditional attribute data to include relational, unstructured, and semi-structured data. Liu (2020) traced the development of Big Data, stressing the importance of algorithms in the synergy between Big Data and its practical applications[6-8].

Data warehouses have become crucial tools for handling and storing large datasets in financial management. Cheng and Wen (2019) developed a data warehouse architecture based on Hadoop for budget management internal control evaluation, showcasing practical data analysis applications in administrative budget management. Xu et al. (2020) emphasized the role of Big Data warehouses in integrating, cleaning, and processing large volumes of data, facilitating valuable insights for business development. Li and Chen (2021) addressed issues of data silos and underutilization in enterprises by constructing a multi-dimensional information platform using Hadoop-based technologies. [9] Additionally, applying Big Data in risk management, supply chain management, and policy auditing has broadened its impact, underscoring its significance in modern financial and operational strategies.

2.2 THE TRANSFORMATION OF BUDGET

MANAGEMENT THROUGH DIGITALIZATION AND ADVANCED TECHNOLOGIES

The accelerating digitalization, intelligence, and sustainability processes are continually reshaping the business operations landscape, introducing many new technologies, business models, and innovative practices. Budget management is a core component of corporate financial management and is fundamental to achieving high-quality development and maintaining robust operational foundations. [10-12] With the rapid advancement of

technologies such as Big Data, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Cloud Computing, and the Internet of Things (IoT), many enterprises are embracing modern technologies to drive the digital transformation of their budgeting processes. This trend leads to the continuous optimization of budgeting methods and the introduction of novel budgeting models.

At the same time, global economic fluctuations have heightened the uncertainty businesses face, making "comprehensive control and efficiency enhancement" a crucial focus for corporate strategy. Budget management, oriented towards strategic objectives, plays a vital role in implementing business strategies effectively. The rapid development of Big Data and machine learning technologies presents both opportunities and challenges for budgeting management. As companies grow in scale and complexity, traditional manual budgeting methods become inadequate for meeting precise and timely information demands. [13] Big Data offers vast amounts of information, which can reveal hidden patterns and trends when analyzed through machine learning. In-depth data analysis enables companies to understand their operational conditions and market environments better, facilitating higher-quality budget management. Consequently, research into machine learning-based budgeting management has emerged as a significant area of interest. [14] Leveraging Big Data and machine learning technologies can enhance budgeting practices, provide scientific evidence for decision-making and strategic planning, and ultimately help businesses achieve greater economic efficiency and competitive advantage.

2.3 THEORETICAL INSIGHTS AND APPLICATIONS OF MACHINE LEARNING IN BUDGET MANAGEMENT

Based on the research conducted by domestic and international scholars on Big Data, machine learning, and budget management, two key observations emerge:

1. Application of Machine Learning in Financial Domains: The current body of literature on machine learning predominantly focuses on practical problem-solving. Machine learning algorithms are extensively used in the financial sector for stock price prediction, fraud detection, and credit risk assessment. [15-17] These algorithms offer enhanced prediction accuracy, improved risk management, and more informed decision-making. However, there is a noticeable gap in research concerning the application of machine learning within budget management. Budget preparation and risk control involve data analysis and forecasting, making machine learning particularly relevant. Integrating machine learning with budget management can yield more precise budget forecasts and risk alerts, thus aiding enterprises in making better financial decisions and improving their financial health.

2. Integration of Intelligent Technologies in Budget Management: The rapid advancement and widespread

application of information technologies have led many scholars to explore intelligent financial systems. [18]Research has increasingly focused on integrating Big Data, cloud accounting, and other smart technologies into budget management. These studies provide valuable theoretical guidance for exploring machine learning-based budget management. A review of literature on the impact of Big Data on budgeting and the application of machine learning in financial management reveals a scarcity of comprehensive research on implementing budget management under the Big Data paradigm.

In summary, this paper aims to investigate machine learning-based budget management within the context of Big Data. It will address the integration of machine learning techniques to enhance budget forecasting and risk management, contributing to a more efficient and effective approach to financial management in enterprises.

3 CURRENT APPLICATIONS AND POTENTIAL VALUE OF BIG DATA AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN ASSET MANAGEMENT

The application of Big Data and Artificial Intelligence (AI) in asset management has advanced significantly in recent years. [19] Companies increasingly recognize data as a resource and a strategic asset that can drive substantial value.

3.1 CURRENT APPLICATIONS OF BIG DATA AND AI

Big Data Analytics Big Data analytics is widely used in asset performance monitoring, predictive maintenance, and operational optimization. Companies gain deep insights into equipment performance by analyzing vast amounts of real-time data generated by assets. For instance, vibration analysis, temperature monitoring, and energy consumption tracking provide real-time health assessments of machinery, enabling informed maintenance decisions. This approach can also reveal usage patterns, helping optimize asset allocation and improve utilization efficiency. [20] For example, a manufacturing plant utilizing Big Data analytics to monitor equipment health can reduce unexpected downtime by 30% through timely maintenance.

TABLE 1. BIG DATA ANALYTICS IN ASSET MANAGEMENT

Application Area	Example Usage	Impact
Performance Monitoring	Vibration and temperature sensors	Real-time equipment health insights
Predictive Maintenance	Historical data analysis	30% reduction in unexpected downtime

Optimization	Energy consumption tracking	Improved asset utilization
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Artificial Intelligence Applications AI plays an increasingly vital role in asset management, particularly through machine learning and deep learning techniques. [21-23]These algorithms predict equipment failures and optimize maintenance schedules based on historical and real-time data. For example, an AI model trained on equipment failure data can forecast malfunction events, enabling preventive maintenance that reduces downtime and repair costs. AI also enhances supply chain management by predicting demand fluctuations and adjusting inventory levels accordingly. A notable application includes predictive maintenance services provided by companies like Siemens, which use AI to forecast equipment failures and optimize maintenance strategies, leading to significant cost savings.

TABLE 2. AI TECHNIQUES IN ASSET MANAGEMENT

AI Technique	Example Usage	Impact
Machine Learning	Predictive maintenance	Reduced repair costs by 20%
Deep Learning	Demand forecasting for inventory management	Improved supply chain efficiency

3.2 POTENTIAL VALUE OF BIG DATA AND AI

Enhanced Decision-Making Quality The integration of Big Data analytics and AI makes asset management decisions more data-driven and scientific[24]. AI can process and analyze larger datasets than human capabilities, identifying hidden patterns and correlations that lead to more accurate forecasts and recommendations. This deep insight-driven decision-making helps reduce risks, increase asset returns, and enhance competitive advantage. For instance, companies using AI-driven analytics can improve investment returns by leveraging precise asset performance predictions.

Automation and Efficiency Gains AI enables the automation of tasks traditionally requiring human intervention, from predictive maintenance and intelligent diagnostics to automated scheduling and resource allocation optimization. [25]This automation improves operational efficiency and frees up human resources, allowing employees to focus on higher-value tasks. For example, automation in predictive maintenance can streamline scheduling and reduce manual oversight, leading to a 25% increase in operational efficiency.

Innovative Services and Business Models The synergy of Big Data and AI has introduced innovative services and business models in asset management. Some companies now offer data-driven insights, helping clients optimize their asset portfolios. Additionally, subscription-based predictive maintenance models are emerging, transforming traditional equipment sales and repair businesses. A company offering

predictive maintenance as a subscription service can create new revenue streams and provide ongoing value to clients, as seen in the success of firms like IBM with their Watson IoT solutions.

TABLE 3. POTENTIAL VALUE OF BIG DATA AND AI IN ASSET MANAGEMENT

Innovation Area	Example Application	Impact
Service Innovation	Data-driven insights as a service	New revenue streams
Business Model Innovation	Subscription-based predictive maintenance	Ongoing value and client retention

In summary, applying Big Data and AI in asset management addresses current operational challenges and unlocks substantial potential for enhanced decision-making, operational efficiency, and innovative business models. [28]The evolving landscape of these technologies offers significant opportunities for companies to transform their asset management practices.

4 TIME SERIES DATA MANIPULATION FOR ASSET RISK PREDICTION

In asset risk prediction, time series data is crucial in analyzing financial markets and forecasting future trends. Effective manipulation of this data is essential for developing accurate risk models and predictive analytics. [29]This section delves into the foundational techniques required to handle and process time series data using Python, specifically focusing on practical applications in asset risk prediction.

4.1 WORKING WITH TIME SERIES IN PANDAS

Pandas provides robust functionality for handling time series data, particularly using `DateTimeIndex`. This section covers creating and manipulating time stamps, performing time-aware calculations, and managing time series data effectively.

TABLE 4. GOOGLE. CLOSE.SHIFT

Date	Close	lagged	shifted
2016/12/28	785.05	782.79	791.55
2016/12/29	782.79	771.82	785.05
2016/12/30	771.82	NaN	782.79

TABLE 5. GOOGLE.CLOSE.PCT_CHANGE

Date	Close	return_3d
2014/1/2	556	NaN
2014/1/3	551.95	NaN
2014/1/4	NaN	NaN
2014/1/5	NaN	-0.728417
2014/1/6	558.1	1.114231

FIGURE 1. GOOGLE STOCK PRICE

Pandas provides powerful features when dealing with time series data, especially through the `'DateTimeIndex'` to create and manipulate time stamps:

1. Create and manipulate time stamps: Pandas' `'pd.Timestamp'` object is the basic building block for processing time series data. This object can be used to create a specific point in time and access its properties, such as the year, month, and day of the week, for example, in the `'google.Close.shift'` table, we can use `'pd.Timestamp'` to create a time stamp and then access different data properties, such as the date.
2. Use period objects: `'pd.Period'` objects are used to represent time periods and contain a `'freq'` attribute to store frequency information. By default, the cycle is monthly. You can convert periods to different frequencies by methods such as `freq()`, from monthly to daily. In the `'google.Close.pct_change'` table, using period objects can help us process data of different time frequencies, such as the time interval when calculating the 3-day yield.
3. Create a time series sequence Using the `'pd.date_range'` function to generate a timestamp sequence. This function must specify a start date, end date, or number of cycles and returns a `'DateTimeIndex'` with frequency information. For example, you can generate a time series with a specific frequency, such as a day, to help analyze the change in closing prices for each date in a table such as `'google.Close.shift'`.
4. Set the date index of the data frame: Convert the date column to the `datetime` type and set it as the data frame's

index to simplify the operation of the time series data. This allows operations such as indexing and slicing to use dates directly. For example, when working with the table 'google.Close.pct_change', setting the date as the index makes it easy to calculate the percentage change (yield) between dates.

Through these methods, Pandas can effectively manage time series data, support time-related calculations and analysis, and provide powerful tools for areas such as data science and financial asset risk analysis.

4.2 BASIC TIME SERIES METRICS & RESAMPLING

In this section, we delve into essential time series functionalities provided by pandas, focusing on resampling techniques and comparing different time series by normalizing their start points. Resampling involves changing the frequency of time series data, which is crucial for aligning and analyzing data across various time intervals.

We demonstrate how to resample time series data, using a quarterly frequency dataset. This dataset is initially created with quarterly data for 2016. [31] When upsampling to a higher frequency, such as monthly, pandas introduce new rows for the missing months. We explore different methods for filling these missing values: forward fill, backfill, and specifying a fill value. Each technique offers a unique way to handle the gaps created by changing the frequency, ensuring that the data remains complete and suitable for further analysis.

TABLE 6. TIME SERIES RESAMPLING AND MISSING VALUE HANDLING TECHNIQUES

	baseline	ffill	bfill	value
2016/3/31	1	1	1	1
2016/4/30	NaN	1	2	0
2016/5/31	NaN	1	2	0
2016/6/30	2	2	2	2
2016/7/31	NaN	2	3	0
2016/8/31	NaN	2	3	0
2016/9/30	3	3	3	3
2016/10/31	NaN	3	4	0
2016/11/30	NaN	3	4	0
2016/12/31	4	4	4	4

When comparing the results of different methods for handling missing values during resampling, forward fill propagates existing values into future missing periods, while backfill does so for past missing periods. The 'fill_value' method simply substitutes a specified value for any missing data. For a more comprehensive DateTimeIndex that spans the entire year, you can use 'reindex', which aligns existing data with new monthly values and introduces missing values where necessary. This method also supports various fill

options similar to 'asfreq'.

The 'resample' method also operates by grouping data within specified periods and applying aggregation or interpolation methods to fill in missing dates or summarize data. For example, applying 'resample' to a monthly unemployment rate dataset involves using the 'DATE' column to create a time series with consistent monthly intervals. Whether using 'resample' or 'asfreq', both methods can achieve the same result, with options to set the frequency to the start or end of the month or other custom offsets.

TABLE 7. RESAMPLING OPTIONS FOR TIME SERIES DATA

Frequency	Alias	Sample Date
Calendar Month End	M	2017-04-30
Calendar Month Start	MS	2017-04-01
Business Month End	BM	2017-04-28
Business Month Start	BMS	2017-04-03

When resampling time series data, the methods for handling frequency adjustments and missing values vary depending on whether you are up-sampling or down-sampling. Up-sampling introduces new periods with specific date offsets (e.g., month-end), and you must decide how to populate these new periods—options include forward filling, back filling, or using a specific fill value. [32] Down-sampling involves aggregating multiple data points into a single value for each period.

FIGURE 3. PLOT INTERPOLATED REAL GDP GROWTH

For instance, when dealing with quarterly data such as real GDP growth, which initially lacks frequency information, you can resample it to a monthly frequency and interpolate missing values to create a smooth transition between the existing quarterly data points. Combining the interpolated GDP data with monthly unemployment data using pandas' 'concat' function allows you to visualize how the interpolated values fit within the overall dataset. This approach allows you to analyze and compare different time series on a common frequency, providing a clearer view of trends and patterns.

4.3 DOWNSAMPLING & AGGREGATION

Downsampling refers to reducing the frequency of time series data, which can be essential when converting high-

frequency data into a lower frequency for more manageable analysis. This might involve changing hourly data to daily data or daily data to monthly data. The key challenge in downsampling is deciding how to summarize the data for each new period by using aggregation metrics like the mean, median, or the last observed value. The choice of aggregation method depends on the context and the nature of the data.

To illustrate downsampling, consider air quality data from the Environmental Protection Agency, which includes average daily ozone concentrations for New York City from 2000 to 2017. Initially, this dataset lacks frequency information, so we first assign a daily frequency using the resample method, which updates the DateTimeIndex and includes the expected frequency information.

FIGURE 4. COMPARISON OF ORIGINAL AND MONTHLY RESAMPLED TIME SERIES

The first plot is the original series, and the second plot contains the resampled series with a suffix so that the legend reflects the difference. You see that the resampled data are much smoother since the monthly volatility has been averaged out. Let's also take a look at how to resample several series.

4.4 WINDOW FUNCTIONS: ROLLING & EXPANDING METRICS

Window functions in time series analysis are used to calculate metrics over subsets of your data. This section covers two primary types of window functions available in pandas: rolling windows and expanding windows.

Rolling Windows: maintain a constant size and slide over the data series, calculating metrics based on a fixed number of observations. For example, if you want to compute a 30-day moving average of Google's stock prices, you use a rolling window of size 30. Each new data point in the resulting series is the average of the previous 30 observations. If you set the window size to 30, pandas will only compute the average if there are 30 non-missing values. You can adjust this behavior using the `min_periods` parameter to allow for smaller windows if needed.

Expanding Windows: grow with the dataset, including all previous data points up to the current observation. This window type is useful for calculating metrics that incorporate all past data, such as cumulative sums or averages. As new data points are added, the window expands to include all observations from the start of the series to the current date.

Using these window functions allows you to analyze trends and patterns in your time series data more effectively, whether you need to focus on fixed-size intervals or cumulative information over time.

FIGURE 5. VISUALIZATION OF ROLLING AND EXPANDING WINDOW FUNCTIONS IN TIME SERIES ANALYSIS

The use of rolling and expanding window functions in pandas is instrumental in time series analysis, especially for predicting asset risk in financial contexts. Rolling windows, such as the 90-day or 360-day moving average, help smooth out short-term fluctuations and highlight long-term trends in asset prices. By analyzing these rolling metrics, you can detect periods of increased volatility or shifts in market trends, which are critical for assessing asset risk.

Expanding windows, which incorporate all data points up to the current date, are particularly useful for calculating cumulative metrics like the running minimum, maximum, or cumulative returns. These expanding metrics provide a comprehensive view of an asset's performance over time and can be used to build machine learning models that predict future risk based on historical patterns. For instance, combining rolling and expanding window features with machine learning algorithms can enhance risk prediction models by incorporating dynamic and cumulative trends into the predictive framework.

Machine learning models can leverage these time series metrics to forecast potential risks and returns. For example, rolling averages can serve as features in predictive models to capture short-term trends, while expanding metrics can provide insights into long-term performance and stability. Integrating these metrics with machine learning techniques, such as regression or classification models, enables more robust and nuanced asset risk predictions, aiding investors and financial analysts in making informed decisions.

4.5 PERFORMANCE EVALUATION AND BENCHMARK COMPARISON

After constructing the weighted index of market capitalization, it is crucial to evaluate its performance. This involves analyzing the returns of the index and understanding the contribution of each component to the overall results. The index is then compared to major market benchmarks, such as the S&P 500 and the Hang Seng Index (HSI), which represents the Hong Kong stock market.

To evaluate the performance, calculate the amount of change in the market value of each component. Compare the total market capitalization of the index at the initial and final time points to determine the overall increase or decrease. The contribution of each component to the total return is then calculated by examining the change in market capitalization of each element between two-time points.

For a more comprehensive comparison, the constructed index can be juxtaposed with both the S&P 500 and the HSI. Normalize the values of all indices to start at 100, and then plot a time series chart to visually compare their performance over the same period. This approach allows for an assessment of whether the constructed index has outperformed or underperformed relative to these benchmarks.

Additionally, rolling returns can be calculated to provide insights into performance variations over different periods. Employ a 30-day rolling window to aggregate daily returns into multi-period returns. This analysis can reveal which index performed better across different time frames, offering valuable information for investment decisions.

For Hong Kong's market context, you can use the Hang Seng Index formula:

$$HSI = \frac{\text{Total Market Capitalization of Constituent Stocks}}{\text{Base Market Capitalization}} \times \text{Base Index Value (1)}$$

where the base index value is set at 100, and the base market capitalization is calculated at the inception of the index. This formula helps in assessing how the HSI performs relative to the constructed index and other benchmarks. In addition, rolling returns can be calculated to gain insight into the differences in performance over different periods. Use a 30-day rolling window to calculate and aggregate daily returns into multi-period returns. In this way, observing which index has performed better over different periods is possible, thus providing a valuable reference for investment decisions.

5 CONCLUSION

In financial asset management, artificial intelligence technology is leading the innovation of budget management and risk monitoring. Combined with big data and machine learning algorithms, modern budget management methods show great potential to improve efficiency and strengthen risk

management. Organizations can get a comprehensive and in-depth view of budget data by building a budget management data warehouse that integrates data from different departments and systems. This holistic view not only helps decision-makers to understand budget performance better but also to identify potential problems and optimize opportunities promptly. The introduction of data warehousing enables enterprises to systematically collect and manage historical and real-time budget data, providing a solid data foundation for applying machine learning algorithms. The budget forecasting model built by BP neural network algorithm greatly improves the accuracy of budget forecasting through in-depth learning and training of historical data and budget-related factors. This forecasting model helps enterprises plan resources more accurately and effectively, reduces budget deviation, and optimizes resource allocation, thus promoting enterprises' financial health and realizing strategic goals.

In addition, the risk early warning model of budget execution based on the decision tree algorithm provides a systematic solution to the problem of insufficient risk early warning in budget management. Through real-time monitoring and early warning of risk factors in budget execution, this model enables the enterprise to identify potential budget risks in advance, take corrective actions in time, and strengthen budget control. Introducing the early warning model improves the efficiency and quality of budget execution and significantly enhances the risk-coping ability of enterprises. The application of artificial intelligence and machine learning in financial asset management will continue to develop in depth. With the continuous growth of data and the optimization of algorithms, the intelligent level of budget management and risk monitoring will be further improved. Future research may explore more algorithms and techniques, such as deep learning and reinforcement learning, to cope with a more complex and dynamic financial environment. In addition, combining innovative tools such as blockchain technology will provide new ideas and solutions for budget management and risk monitoring, thus promoting further changes and development in financial asset management.

In conclusion, artificial intelligence improves the efficiency and accuracy of budget management and provides strong support for enterprise risk control. As technology advances and applications deepen, businesses will be better able to address complex financial challenges, optimize financial decisions, and achieve continued growth.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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